

Analysis of tourist services market development in Surkhandarya region

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Abstract. *Currently, tourism is one of the fastest growing sectors of the economy in many regions of the world. The tourism industry has become the third largest sector of the world economy. The fact that the UN named 2017 as the "International Year of Sustainable Tourism" is a clear proof of our words.*

Keywords: *market, service, guests, supply, demand.*

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is a powerful catalyst for the economic development of developed and developing countries, provides the flow of foreign currency and investments, contributes to the rapid growth of related industries, helps to solve the problems of population employment, and increases the country's reputation in the world community. It is possible to ensure a large amount of foreign exchange in the tourism sector with much less expenditure compared to other sectors.

In terms of globalization, there are unsolved scientific issues regarding increasing the competitiveness of regions and assessing the degree of connection with the development of its economy. Therefore, it is necessary to formulate and implement strategies for the development of tourism enterprises, to implement the issue of coordinating production activities with the requirements of the domestic and foreign markets based on their information.

In the Surkhandarya region, based on the target programs for the rapid development of the tourism sector using the available resources, the creation of new jobs, the increase of incomes and living standards of the population, and the increase of investment attractiveness, the transformation of the tourism sector into one of the leading industries in the region is being carried out in the following strategic directions:

- creation of favorable conditions for the development of tourism in the region;
- preservation of tourist resources of the region and their increase;
- formation of touristic and satellite infrastructure, improvement of their activity;
- improvement of transport logistics and service provision;
- creation of own brands of the region, development of new tourist routes and types of products;

- improvement of the system of training of qualified personnel, retraining and upgrading of skills of employees operating in the field.

Recreational bases in Sherabad, Boysun, Uzun, Sarosiyoy, Denov, Altisoy districts, where there are convenient opportunities for local and foreign tourists to have a short-term rest in the heart of nature and to restore their health in areas with high tourist potential in the first direction. private houses, seasonal children's summer camps should be turned into official business entities operating in the field of tourism providing services to visitors.

The action strategy for the establishment and support of business entities in the field of tourism shows the existence of an informal sector despite the reforms implemented within the framework of the Presidential Decrees and the need to take measures to transfer them to official activities.

To establish official local tourism business entities, they should:

- establishing a special source of financing or directing funds from the tourism development fund to projects in small tourism zones in the region;
- introducing a special procedure for taxation;
- allocation of preferential medium and long-term credit funds;
- it is necessary to explain that it is possible to improve the infrastructure of the area where they live, to improve the quality of service, to increase the number of visitors, to create more jobs, and to increase the amount of income.

In the second direction, development of targeted programs to gradually turn more than 700 cultural heritage objects in the region into tourist attractions, including the conversion of Sultan Saodat Complex, Kirghiz Castle, Kokildar Father's Shrine, Sufi Olloyoy, Khujja Alauddin Attar, Maulana Muhammed Zahid shrines to Islam. preparation for the visit of local and foreign pilgrims who believe, preparation of Buddhist temples and facilities such as Dalvarzintepa, Fayoztepa, Karatepa, Zurmula, Kampirtepa for foreign pilgrims and local visitors who believe in Buddhism, and the creation of tourism infrastructure. It is necessary to increase the number of museums displaying archaeological exhibits found in these cultural heritage sites.

In the third direction, tourist infrastructure in the mountain and sub-mountain zones of Termiz, Boysun, Sherabad, Oltinsoy, Denov, Sariosiyoy, Uzun districts, including hostels with cheap accommodation for local tourists, family guest houses, modern hotels that meet international requirements for foreign tourists, it is necessary to establish the activity of tourist bases, treatment and health facilities, to create conditions for the establishment of integrated tourism complexes consisting of facilities, trade and general catering centers with the possibility of holding various cultural, entertainment, sports events, which are considered as companion infrastructure.

In the development of the tourism sector, the organization of small tourism zones, the improvement of business activities in the tourism sector by attracting foreign investments, the effective use of natural factors, the involvement of technologies that meet the requirements of the present time, the provision of high-quality services and tourist services to the international and domestic markets, the amount of export of services increase, improve the tourism infrastructure, further increase the employment of the population, and provide quality services to tourists, allowing to develop the socio-economic sphere by achieving a further increase in the flow of tourists.

The organizational and economic mechanism for establishing the activity of small tourism zones should be developed based on local conditions, for this purpose:

First, it is necessary to ensure that villages and neighborhoods in small tourism zones are given the status of "Tourism village" and "Tourism neighborhood". Regions with this status will have the following opportunities:

- By entering the "Prosperous Village" program, electricity, gas, water supply, sewage system will be fundamentally improved and their stable operation will be achieved;
- roads will be repaired and the area will be improved;
- the activity of base stations will be launched to improve the quality of mobile communication and internet network.

Secondly, it will be possible to create recreational-tourist clusters in small tourism zones. According to the experience of foreign countries, the complexity of the cluster approach is related to sectoral and national factors. However, 12 clusters can be characterized by characteristics such as: availability of research and development opportunities, skills of the workforce, development of human resources potential, availability of specific types of services, proximity of suppliers, availability of funds, relations with equipment suppliers, organizational structures, networking intensity, entrepreneurial spirit, innovation and learning, team leadership. As a very important indicator, the special labor force is of particular importance, and it is considered the most important and mandatory element of the regional cluster program. In order to establish touristic recreation clusters, first of all, there should be parties that will be its members, there are no such officially operating service and competing objects in the regions of the region, or there are many competitors. It is appropriate to use the mechanism of public and private partnership on the basis of alternatives in the transfer of business activities in the provision of tourism services to the local population to continue in the official sector.

As a result of the cooperation of state and private entrepreneurs, in addition to having advantages such as effective use of budget funds or state extra-budgetary financial funds, increase in the amount of allocated funds, local residents and visitors are also considered to be interested.

Development of entrepreneurship in small tourism zones, implementation of an active policy on attracting foreign and local investors, increasing the prestige of the region is one of the urgent issues, construction, repair and improvement of social and transport infrastructures; organization and development of information networks; personnel training and retraining; it is necessary to pay attention to the organization of market infrastructure, including marketing service, commercial information systems.

A number of activities are being carried out in the region to attract foreign investors. In particular, in cooperation with Turkish investors, the technical and economic basis of the Boysun tourism center was developed, according to which the investment project with a total cost of 140,896,000 US dollars for 2020-2040 is planned to be implemented in 4 stages.

According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 27, 2020 No. 332 "On effective use of the tourism potential of the Surkhandarya region and additional measures for its development", further development of the tourism potential of the region, wide introduction of tourists to the unique historical, cultural and architectural monuments of the region, Based on regional

investment programs of Surkhandarya region in order to rapidly develop modern tourism infrastructure and improve the quality of tourism services, to activate domestic tourism, create new jobs and stimulate the growth of population income:

Creating more than 1,115 new places of employment by building 20 hotels;

organization of 4 health centers for 170 places;

Establishment of 60 family guest houses with 487 beds was decided.

In addition, the establishment of 6 craft centers and service facilities around large pilgrimage tourism objects, all cultural heritage objects, shrines, museums, hotels, craft centers and other tourism objects visited by tourists in Surkhandarya region, as well as crowded places, in particular markets, Shah Issues such as stations, service stations along the road, establishment of VI-FI zones in recreational parks, establishment of tourism information centers in places frequented by tourists, in particular, in the Termiz Archeology Museum and regional history and culture museums, were determined.

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